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TITLE

2 THE SELF-SIMULATION THEORY:A COMPUTATIONAL THEORY OF CONSCIOUSNESS

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AUTHORS

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5 **ABSTRACT**

6 The current theories of consciousness do not address the two major problems:What is the solution to
7 the hard problem of consciousness or What is the experience of self-existence? and How is conscious
8 perception computed? We address these questions using our hypothesized theory:The Self Simulation
9 theory and propose a model of computation of consciousness.The components of the model are an
10 interconnected network of auxiliary processors or Auxiliary Neural Networks(AN) which receives
11 input from the external sensory modalities,computes a representation of the information and relays it to
12 the NCC(Neural Correlates of Consciousness), the NCC – a processing unit which can be neuro
13 anatomically distributed in location but computationally connected to each other and to the Auxiliary
14 Networks,and a working memory which the NCC references for further computation of
15 information.Computation of conscious perception is achieved via the decoding of the content of the
16 memory by the NCC.The self simulation theory accounts not only for the various phenomenal
17 experiences but also experimentation paradigms conducted in the past.

18 INTRODUCTION

19 Consciousness as stated by Chalmers¹ is anything that we experience, from perceiving the color of
20 red, the depth of thought, smell of a flower, sound of a guitar, pleasure of orgasms to the agony of
21 pain. Over the years many people have tried to explain the phenomenon of consciousness. Descartes
22 gave the homunculus concept, a homunculus viewing contents in a tiny theater in brain². Dennet
23 disapproves of the casting of analyzed data in the “Cartesian theater” in brain and gives the multiple
24 drafts theory³. Crick and Koch gave the neurobiological theory of consciousness⁴ and also proposed a
25 framework of consciousness⁵. Other theories proposed are the global workspace theory⁸, global neuronal
26 workspace theory¹⁰, and recurrent processing theory¹¹ suggesting the neural correlates of consciousness
27 to be a global neuronal workspace and a local recurrent processing network respectively. Giulio Tononi
28 proposed the Integrated Information Theory⁶⁻⁷, where a sufficiently complex and integrated information
29 processing network is deemed to be conscious.

30 However the current theories of consciousness fail to explain the hard problem of consciousness- “How
31 do we perceive an experience? How do we perceive self existence?”¹ Also they fail to explain the
32 computation behind a conscious experience- “What is the exact mechanism by which an external
33 sensory modality is perceived as a conscious experience?”

34 We resolve to solve the problems stated above by directly targeting the notion of perception. Marr⁶⁶
35 argued that there are three levels of analysis for every information processing system: Computational:
36 stating the problem to be solved, Algorithmic: giving the algorithm to solve the problem and
37 Implementational: how the algorithm is implemented in the physical hardware of the system. In this
38 paper we aim to address the computational aspect of the information processing required to generate a
39 conscious perception. We propose the existence of a processing unit which can be neuro anatomically
40 distributed in location but computationally connected, which we call the neural correlate of
41 consciousness (NCC). This processing unit will be bidirectionally connected to a working memory, thus
42 giving NCC access to its past state. To tackle the hard problem of consciousness we propose that there
43 is no real perception or experience, rather it's just the format information is stored and processed by
44 NCC. Hence, the perception of self-existence is just a simulation generated by the computation
45 between the NCC and its memory, giving the name: The Self Simulation Theory.

46 PRESENTATION OF THE HYPOTHESIS:

47 Consider that you are deprived of our vision, you will experience a feeling of lack of vision. Similarly if
48 you are deprived of your other sensory modalities one by one, you will experience a feeling of lack of
49 smell, taste, touch so on and so forth. It has been reported that patients with akinetic mutism, in spite of
50 loss of emotional and goal directed behavior, have an intact level of consciousness⁵⁷.
51 Thus this suggests that the neural network generating the feeling of consciousness should function
52 independent of the external sensory, emotional and behavioral modalities. Thus we categorize the
53 existence of the various sensory, emotional, behavioral, attention and cognitive networks to be auxiliary
54 networks to the network producing sensation of consciousness, also called NCC (Neural Correlates
55 of Consciousness).

56 Figure 1:This figure demonstrates the computational architecture we hypothesize. ‘a’:referencing of the
 57 stored information by the NCC for further computation and generation of conscious perception.,
 58 ‘b’:NCC stores relevant information needed for its next cycle of computation,i e the content of
 59 consciousness,in its working memory.,’c’:bi-directional information relay between the auxiliary
 60 networks and the NCC., ‘d’:information transfer between the various auxiliary networks causing
 61 computational integration in a distributed system of auxiliary networks., ‘e’:motor response relayed
 62 from auxiliary network to the external motor modalities., ‘f’:information input from external sensory
 63 modality to the auxiliary network layer.

64 **Auxiliary Network(AN)**

65 An auxiliary network acts a bridge between the environment and the NCC.It computes information
 66 relayed by various modalities like peripheral sensory receptors,eyes,ears,taste buds and form a
 67 representation of the modality for input to the NCC(‘f’ in Figure 1).The auxiliary network also
 68 comprises of the motor system,which receives input from the NCC and converts it to an executable
 69 form(‘e’ in Figure 1).

70 An auxiliary network will have the following properties:

71 1) The network consists of functionally and computationally connected neural networks

72 Consider the topography of the brain to consist of a complex interconnected network of neurons. Over
73 the years there have been a large number of studies in the field of network analysis and cognitive
74 computational neuroscience²²⁻³² to explore and model various cognitive domains, like
75 attention: visuospatial attention¹²⁻¹³ endogenous attention network¹⁴ ventral and dorsal attention
76 networks¹⁵, emotion¹⁶, language¹⁷, memory¹⁸, audition¹⁹, sensory motor²⁰, thought generation²¹, so on
77 and so forth. These approaches prove that cognitive neural architecture is a distributed neural network
78 processing that are computationally connected to generate a representation of a cognitive domain. We
79 call these neural architectures as auxiliary networks. These do not generate perception of cognition.
80 They are merely auxiliary to the neural correlates of consciousness(NCC).

81 2) The network should be computationally and neuronally connected to the NCC:

82 As we have already discussed, the auxiliary networks do not compute conscious perception of
83 cognition. They merely compute a representation of the cognitive domain. Thus these auxiliary
84 networks are unconscious in nature. The computation of conscious perception is done by NCC. Thus in
85 order to relay information for integration the auxiliary networks have to be connected both
86 computationally and neuronally to the NCC('c' in Figure 1).

87 3) The connection between AN and NCC should be functionally bi-directional:

88 Consider the following thought experiment: You are in a room where there is a table with an apple on
89 top of it. You are seeing the entire scene, including the table, the apple and the room. When you are
90 asked, "Do you see an apple?" You will search for it in the room and probably reply that you can see an
91 apple on the table. This is because of visual attention. Here the information of the scenic representation
92 will be integrated by the NCC along with other information inputs from the memory network, language
93 network, attention network, etc. The NCC will direct the visual attention network to shift attention to
94 that of the apple. Then instead of the entire scenic representation, representation of the apple will reach
95 the NCC. Similarly other phenomenological experiences like recursive thought generation, imagination
96 and others consider that there must be bi-directional computation and functionality between the various
97 auxiliary networks and NCC('c' in Figure 1).

98 There can be multiple ANs, interconnected with each other:

99 Studies have shown that damage to white matter can cause damage to multiple cognitive
100 domains(33). According to network analysis studies the cognitive domains are interconnected via
101 network architecture(21). Thus the various auxiliary networks like visual, auditory, motor and others can
102 be interconnected to compute the various cognitive processes('d' in Figure 1).

103 **Neural Correlates of Consciousness(NCC)**

104 The term NCC or Neural correlates of consciousness was introduced by Koch and Crick⁴ to explain the
105 specific mechanism or system responsible for the state of consciousness.

106 Properties of NCC:

107 1)Performs information integration across various auxiliary networks:

108 NCC helps to answer the binding problem introduced by Damasio³⁴.Information relayed by various
109 auxiliary networks will be integrated by the NCC.(‘c’ in Figure 1) Then a output command is computed
110 by the NCC to direct the auxiliary network for further computation.(‘c’ in Figure 1)

111 2)Performs discrete information processing:

112 NCC integrates information from auxiliary networks in discrete time intervals.
113 In one cycle of computation,NCC takes in information from auxiliary networks and then processes the
114 information for a fixed time period. During this time period the NCC cannot integrate further
115 information from the auxiliary networks.

116 3)Possesses an intrinsic memory network:

117 NCC possesses an intrinsic memory network.
118 This memory is a type of working memory. NCC stores information being processed in a single cycle
119 of computation which it deems to be important for integration in the next cycle of computation,in its
120 memory(‘b’ in Figure 1).Due to this property of referencing of previous memory(‘a’ in Figure 1),the
121 connection between the NCC and the memory network is bidirectional in nature. This cycle of
122 computation and referencing the working memory continues infinitely across the temporal dimension.

123 **COMPUTATION OF CONSCIOUSNESS**

124 Chalmers states that the hard problem of consciousness is to find out why a conscious organism
125 experiences a feeling of self existence¹.

126 According to our hypothesis when the NCC performs information integration from various auxiliary
127 inputs,it stores certain important information in its working memory,which needs to be integrated in its
128 next cycle of computation.Now the information being stored is dependent upon the type,content and
129 importance of each auxiliary network which will input the information of the peripheral modalities or
130 external world to the NCC. While storing the information in the memory it is stored in the format of
131 self perception of the information. In other words,the NCC will compute the solution to the problem “If
132 the organism is perceiving the following auxiliary information,what will be the relevant information to
133 be stored in its memory and what will be the response to the perceived information?” To this
134 question,the memory stores the relevant information and response in the format of “The organism is
135 perceiving the information and an action was taken in lieu of it.”

136 The NCC,when referencing the working memory for its next cycle of computation can decode the type
137 and content of information stored in the memory due to a predefined notion of what a particular type of
138 information can entail. This decoding of the content of the working memory is what gives rise to the
139 feeling of consciousness.

140 The NCC thus computes a sense of perception of self existence. There is no predefined area of brain
141 dedicated to perception of self existence. Similarly there is no particular area of brain dedicated to
142 perceive what is to be in a particular cognitive state,i e perception of touch,vision,audition,so on and so
143 forth.

144 Consider the following thought experiments:

145 Figure 2. This figure demonstrates the computational framework of a thought experiment of getting
 146 pricked by a thorn and withdrawing hand in response. 'a':The memory is referenced by the NCC in the
 147 subsequent cycle of computation giving rise to conscious perception, 'b':NCC computes the content of
 148 conscious perception of pain and a response in lieu of it and stores the content in its memory, ('c1','c2',
 149 'c3'):information regarding representation of pain is relayed to the NCC from the auxiliary network
 150 layer, 'c4':information regarding response to the perception of pain is relayed from the NCC to the
 151 auxiliary motor network, 'd':intercommunication between the auxiliary networks, 'e1':the information
 152 sent to the peripheral pain apparatus is relayed to the auxiliary pain network, 'e2':motor information is
 153 relayed from the auxiliary motor network to the external motor apparatus, 'f1':the information
 154 conveyed by prick of thorn is relayed to peripheral pain apparatus, 'f2':the external motor apparatus
 155 carries out the response.

156 1)You are pricked with a thorn in your hand. You will report that you are feeling pain and will move
157 your hand away. The feeling of pain is the feeling of self existence. Now how is this generated. When
158 you are pricked,the peripheral pain receptors and neurons will relay the information to the auxiliary
159 pain networks('f1', 'e1' in Figure 2). The auxiliary networks form a representation of the pain
160 modality. This information is relayed to the NCC('c1', 'c2', 'c3' in Figure 2). The NCC computes the
161 solution to the problem "If you are perceiving the information regarding representation of pain what is
162 the most relevant information to be stored in the memory and what is the appropriate response?" The
163 memory stores information in the form of "I am feeling the representation of pain and my hand should
164 be withdrawn."('b' in Figure 2). Further the NCC directs the auxiliary motor network to withdraw the
165 hand from the site of pain('c4' in Figure 2).The auxiliary motor network in turn directs the peripheral
166 motor apparatus to withdraw the hand.('e2', 'f2' in Figure 2).NCC references its memory in the next
167 cycle of computation and decodes the information stored in it.('a' in Figure 2) Information is
168 interpreted as "I felt a sense of pain and I withdrew my hand in response".Thus the perception of pain
169 is a result of the computation of the NCC and its memory.

170 Figure 3. This figure demonstrates the computational framework of a thought experiment of seeing a
 171 rose. 'a':The memory is referenced by the NCC in the subsequent cycle of computation giving rise to
 172 conscious perception, 'b':NCC computes the content of conscious perception of pain and a response in
 173 lieu of it and stores the content in its memory, ('c1', 'c2', 'c3', 'c4'):information regarding
 174 representation of the rose is relayed to the NCC from the auxiliary network layer,
 175 'd':intercommunication between the auxiliary networks, 'e':the information from the eye is relayed to
 176 the auxiliary visual network, 'f':the information conveyed by the rose is relayed to the eye.

177 2)There is a rose in front of you. The modal information reaches the visual cortex,where a
 178 representation of the rose is computed('f', 'e' in Figure 3).This information is relayed by the visual
 179 auxiliary network to the

180 NCC('c1', 'c2', 'c3', 'c4').The NCC computes the solution to the problem, "If you are perceiving the
181 information regarding representation of a rose what is the most relevant information to be stored in the
182 memory and what is the appropriate response?" The memory will store information in the form of "I
183 am seeing a rose."('b' in Figure 3) This information will be decoded by the NCC in the next cycle of
184 computation, giving you the perception of seeing the rose.('a' in Figure 3) Thus the perception of
185 seeing the rose or the perception of any other cognitive state is merely a decoding of the content of the
186 working memory by the NCC.

187 **TESTING THE HYPOTHESIS:**

188 In this section we will report studied phenomenal experiences and experimentation paradigms and
189 explain their causation using our proposed theory. We also report the proposed experimentation and
190 simulations that can be performed to test our hypothesized model.

191 **Slowing down of events during traumatic incidents:**

192 Studies over the years have reported that there is a subjective experience of slowing down of
193 events in traumatic incidents,also known as "bullet time"³⁵⁻³⁶.
194 During a traumatic event there is a state of panic in the brain. There is heightened alertness or attention
195 in the sensory,emotional,motor and other cognitive networks, causing increased computation of the
196 auxiliary networks. Due to this there is an increased influx of information to the NCC for being
197 computed. To compensate for the increased requirements of computational power, the NCC increases its
198 cycle number per unit time. The duration of one computational cycle decreases. Thus the computation
199 time for an event registered by the memory of NCC will be of much smaller duration than the actual
200 timing of the event in the external reality. In other words, the external environment gets slower relative
201 to NCC. Thus the external reality will be perceived as a delayed or slowed down event with respect to
202 the internal state of NCC's computation.

203 **Subjective experience of time dilation:**

204 Studies have reported incidents of subjective experience of time dilation in boredom and time
205 contraction in cases of having fun³⁷. According to various psychological models of time perception like
206 the pacemaker - accumulator model⁶⁰ and the attention gate model⁶¹, attention will dictate the number
207 of pulses being transferred from the pacemaker to the accumulator. Greater the the count of pulses
208 stored by the accumulator greater will be the perception of time dilation and vice versa⁵⁹.
209 The model we propose is in agreement with the attention gate model. Amount of attention being
210 allocated to time will dictate the computation of the "time" variable by the NCC. The time count will
211 be stored by the NCC in its functional working memory after every cycle of computation,in the form of
212 "I am perceiving the passage of n number of counts." This is decoded by the NCC in its next cycle of
213 computation,giving rise to the perception of passage of time.
214 Normally there is no significant attention being paid to time or its passage in day to day life. However
215 during boredom,there is increased attention being paid to time,due to decreased attention to external
216 cues. This will cause a greater time count to be stored in the working memory of NCC, leading to a
217 perception of time dilation. Thus There is no real time dilation here, only increased awareness of
218 passage of time. Similarly in cases of having fun, there is decreased attention being paid to
219 time,because of increased attention being paid to the external cue. This will cause decreased time
220 computation by NCC,causing a reduced time count to be stored in its memory and thus leading to a

221 perception of time contraction or “flying” of time. Thus There is no real time contraction here, only
222 decreased awareness of passage of time.

223 **Working Awareness:**

224 Crick and Koch⁴ have used “fleeting awareness” to describe a type of transient awareness or attention
225 with a large one time capacity and ability to focus on certain relevant items or features, bound
226 epigenetically or over learned, for further processing. This means that you are not attending to all the
227 things in your visual field.

228 Consider two objects-A and B in your visual field. Information regarding both the objects will be
229 relayed by the peripheral sensory modalities to the auxiliary networks. Information about both object A
230 and B being relayed to the NCC. NCC decides whether object A or B is important depending upon
231 various auxiliary network inputs-memory, sensory, thought generation, and others. In subsequent cycles
232 of computation, NCC will order the ANs to send more information about the attended object, giving
233 rise to working awareness. The duration of awareness will depend upon the extent of computation of
234 NCC and the incoming information from the auxiliary networks.

235 **Split brain phenomenon:**

236 Figure 4.This figure demonstrates the computational architecture of the phenomenon of split brain.
237 'a':verbal auxiliary network, 'b':right motor auxiliary network, 'c':right visual auxiliary network.

238 Split brain refers to patients in whom the corpus callosum is cut for relieving medically untreatable
239 epilepsy. Studies by Gazzaniga, Sperry and colleagues⁵¹⁻⁵³ have shown using contra lateral domains like
240 vision and touch, that in a split brain person, after presentation of an external cue in their left visual
241 field, can point to the cue with their left hand but reports to seeing nothing when asked.
242 There is no known fixed neuro anatomical location of the NCC. NCC may be distributed
243 computationally or neuro anatomically between the two cerebral hemispheres. The visual information
244 from the external cue in the left visual field is processed by the auxiliary visual networks of the right
245 visual cortex(Left visual field to 'c' in Figure 4). This information is relayed to the the NCC in the right
246 cerebral hemisphere.The NCC will compute the response for relaying to the right motor cortex and
247 direct it to point towards the cue('c' to 'b' in Figure 4). Since the cortex cortices control contralateral
248 body parts mostly,the left hand will point towards the cue('b' to Left side response in Figure 4).
249 However since the verbal auxiliary network is concentrated in the left hemisphere resulting in no
250 communication between the NCC in the right hemisphere and the verbal network('c' to 'a' in Figure 4).
251 Thus, even though the perception of vision occurs in the right NCC, the verbal network does not
252 receive any information.
253 We propose that both hemispheres have independent NCCs. When they are connected by corpus
254 callosum, they function as a single unit and give rise to a unified consciousness⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶. When corpus
255 callosum is cut, they become separated and form two independent conscious entities. In other words
256 give rise to split consciousness⁵¹⁻⁵².

257 **Afferent signals do not directly contribute to conscious perception of external modalities:**

258 Charles Bonnet syndrome is a syndrome of having visual hallucinations with impairment of vision due
259 to macular degeneration or diabetic retinopathy with old age³⁹.Studies have reported auditory
260 hallucinations in deaf individuals⁴⁰.Similarly there have been studies reporting retaining of conscious
261 perception in setting of stroke or lesion of certain cortices.
262 When sensory afferents do not relay information to the auxiliary networks, these networks can either
263 perform random or erroneous computation of information. Thus NCC will receive a random or
264 erroneous input from the auxiliary networks. Depending upon the type of auxiliary network giving
265 input, the NCC will compute a perception of that cognitive domain. Subjects have reported to see
266 hallucinations of their past memories in Charles Bonnet syndrome. This indicates that the visual
267 auxiliary networks can relay information from the long term memory networks and perform erroneous
268 or random computation to render information to the NCC. The NCC will perceive the information as an
269 input from the visual auxiliary network and thus compute the perception of vision.In stroke patients,
270 after destruction of some portion of the cortex, they loss some aspect of a sensory modalities or
271 completely loss the modality,yet they remain conscious.
272 Thus external sensory modalities or even a particular single auxiliary network do not contribute to
273 consciousness. There may be loss of perception of a particular sensation but that does not result in the
274 loss of consciousness.

275 **Efferent signals do not directly contribute to conscious perception:**

276 The locked-in syndrome is a type of disorder in which a person is aware and conscious but are devoid
277 of various efferent systems-speech, facial, limb movements, except for vertical eye movements and

278 blinking³⁸. Similarly sleep paralysis is a state of REM paralysis when the person is still conscious and
279 aware of his surroundings⁶². Many patients get paralyzed after stroke in the motor cortex, yet retain their
280 consciousness.

281 The NCC computes the information stream from the auxiliary network to generate a response and the
282 content of conscious perception to be stored in its memory for the next cycle of computation. If the
283 motor auxiliary network is inhibited or compromised, the response computed by the NCC will not get
284 an external representation. But inability of the motor auxiliary networks can not affect the the
285 computation of NCC. Thus there is a conscious perception of the external environment in spite of
286 having no efferent connections or motor response.

287

288 **Blindsight:**

289 Blindsight is defined as the ability to possess goal directed behavior towards an external cue in a person
290 with damage to primary visual cortex⁴³⁻⁴⁵.

291 Information about the external environment is transferred to NCC via various ANs. Studies have
292 reported that the visual pathway mediated by the superior colliculus, the pulvinar and the extra striate
293 visual areas is involved in blindsight circuitry⁴⁶. These neuro anatomical regions may house certain
294 auxiliary networks that can transfer the information to the NCC. Since in these conditions, there is no
295 intact visual auxiliary network to transfer external information to the NCC, there is no perception of
296 vision. However the incoming information can go to other interconnected networks like thought
297 generation network, memory network, so and so forth. The computed information can then go into NCC
298 and can influence the decision by the NCC through an indirect pathway, causing the action of pointing
299 towards the external cue.

300 **Masked priming experiments:**

301 Studies have presented visual words (prime) masked by nonsense letters for a very brief duration (43
302 ms) so that it cannot be seen but nevertheless facilitates the subsequent processing of shown related
303 words (target). This phenomenon is called masked priming⁴¹.

304 We can attribute this phenomenon to the impaired information transfer between NCC and the auxiliary
305 networks. Upon seeing the prime, the information is relayed to the visual auxiliary networks, however
306 due to such small duration of presence, the information is considered unimportant for further
307 processing by the visual AN. Thus this information is not sent to the NCC. However the information of
308 prime is still being stored among the auxiliary networks and can influence subsequent information
309 processing of the visual and other ANs. Thus, in the subsequent processing, information about the
310 target thus gets increased importance and is sent to the NCC for conscious perception by the auxiliary
311 networks. So the prime helps in the subsequent processing of the target though it is not consciously
312 perceived.

313 **Proposed experimentation paradigm:**

314 We propose certain experimentation paradigms that we deem will be useful in testing our hypothesized
315 theory.

316 1) Testing the discreteness of information processing of NCC:

317 In order to determine the discreteness of NCC's information processing we need to conduct simple
318 psychological experiments to estimate the interval of computation of NCC. Information regarding
319 further experimentation will be provided in later papers.

320 2)Simulation of the model:

321 Computer simulations of the proposed model need to be created to estimate its efficacy in reproducing
322 the perception of consciousness and to execute cognitive functions. Once we can simulate the
323 functioning of NCC and its working memory, we will be able to know the content of the memory, i.e. the
324 content of conscious perception. Monitoring the evolution of conscious perceptions by administering
325 external stimulus to the simulation and simultaneously the actual person will allow us to evaluate the
326 effectiveness of our model and ultimately decode the exact computational algorithm.

327 **IMPLICATION OF THEORY:**

328 It is important to mention the various implications or conclusions that we derive about consciousness,
329 its computation and its perception using the self simulation theory.

330 **Consciousness is the ability to perceive self existence**

331 Consciousness as stated by Nagel⁶³ is to have the experience of being a conscious organism, in other
332 words the perception of self existence. Even after removal of all external sensory and motor modalities
333 there is still a feeling of self existence and the perception of the lack there of.

334 **Conscious perception is a simulation generated by NCC's computation**

335 We have already stated that the conscious perception is a result of decoding of the memory's content by
336 the NCC and that there is no such experience of cognitive domains rather the perception is due to the
337 format of information stored in the memory of NCC.

338 **Content of consciousness is the content of the working memory of NCC**

339 The NCC computes the information incoming from the auxiliary networks and stores relevant
340 information in the memory, for use in its next cycle of computation. This information being stored in
341 the memory of NCC is the content of conscious experience and is decoded by the NCC to generate the
342 perception of consciousness.

343 **Consciousness is self referential and self sustainable**

344 We have already established that conscious perception does not need any afferent or efferent signals to
345 exist. It is a computational product of NCC and its working memory and is thus self sustainable.
346 The memory is referenced by the NCC for its next cycle of computation to compute a response for the
347 incoming stream of information and is thus self referential in nature.

348 **Consciousness is discretely computed but has a continuous temporal distribution**

349 The NCC performs computation in a discrete manner, which means there is a particular time interval
350 for which NCC computes and does not admit further information input from the auxiliary networks.
351 The memory of NCC is updated every cycle of computation resulting in a discrete computation of the
352 content of consciousness, continuing infinitely across the temporal dimension.

353 **For a system to be conscious it must have access to its immediate past state**

354 We propose a basic theory of computation needed to generate consciousness. According to our theory
355 any system which has access to its immediate past state i.e. information about its existence in the past is
356 conscious. The NCC stores information in its working memory in the form of “the organism is
357 perceiving the incoming information”.The NCC in its next cycle of computation, decodes the memory
358 content and simulates a conscious perception of the event.

359 **Consciousness is an all or none phenomenon but its contents can be graded**

360 We consider consciousness to be a state which either exists or not. However the content of
361 consciousness is decided by the computation of NCC and the amount of external input it gets. The
362 computation of NCC again depends on the level of activation or complexity of the integrated
363 networks. Thus simpler systems fulfilling the criteria of consciousness, with lesser integration with
364 other auxiliary networks and lesser network activation, will have a perception that has lesser
365 dimensions in terms of experience.

366 **Conscious perception cannot be subjectively verified or falsified**

367 The NCC is involved in storing the content of a conscious experience and decoding it to generate the
368 respective conscious perception. We are all having an illusion of the simulation computed by the NCC.
369 We can not subjectively verify or falsify the claim of having conscious perception,as any conscious
370 perception is a result of NCC’s simulation and we have no way to go around it.

371 **DISCUSSION**

372 We propose in this paper the self-simulation theory,a model that performs cognitive processing and
373 simulates conscious perception of self existence. The basic architecture of our model is the existence of
374 auxiliary networks,the NCC and working memory for NCC. The auxiliary networks perform
375 computation about information received from the external modalities and relay a representation of it to
376 the NCC. The NCC in turn computes the answer to the question “If the organism is perceiving the
377 representation of the external modality then what is the necessary information to be stored in its
378 memory and what is the response to the incoming information?” The memory stores information in the
379 format “the organism is perceiving the information computed by NCC.” The memory’s content is
380 referenced and decoded in the next cycle of NCC’s computation,generating the perception of
381 consciousness. Thus we conclude that conscious perception is a simulation carried out by the
382 computation between NCC and its memory.

383 The Global Workspace Theory of Consciousness⁸ (GWT) states that conscious perception involves a
384 wide distribution of a focal information to recruit other neural resources for information processing. We
385 refer to this distribution of information processors as a distribution of auxiliary networks,integrated
386 together to perform information processing. GWT suggests existence of attention codelets,which
387 capture important features from the incoming information and compete for access to global workspace.
388 This information is stored in a “fleeting” global workspace memory and is broadcast⁹.This broadcasted
389 information is ultimately processed by the distributed network of information processors,giving a
390 cognitive basis to the conscious experience. The Global Neuronal Workspace theory¹⁰ also supports the
391 existence of a global neuronal workspace,which gives rise to conscious perception via broadcasting to
392 certain specialized processors.However these theories do not answer the questions of “How is the
393 existence of self perceived?” “What is the NCC?” or “When is an organism conscious?” We suggest the
394 existence of the NCC as a processing unit which can be neuro anatomically distributed in location but

395 computationally connected. The NCC has a working memory referenced as “Global Workspace
396 Memory”, which stores the information needed for the next cycle of NCC’s computation. The content of
397 NCC’s memory is the content of conscious experience and is perceived via decoding of the memory’s
398 content in the next cycle of NCC’s computation.

399 The Integrated Information Theory⁶⁻⁷ states that the neural substrates of consciousness is the main
400 complex of neural networks with well integrated information processing and high Φ value. This
401 conscious experience cannot be altered by altering the external complex of neural networks. However it
402 does not explain how the conscious perception of self is generated. The NCC is defined as the
403 minimum neural system which directly correlates with states of consciousness⁶⁴. Thus if we were to
404 keep the NCC in any other state, there would be no conscious state. However if we were to change the
405 network architecture in the main complex or as mentioned by Tononi et al.⁶, removing the red sensitive
406 network within the color sensitive network of the main complex, according to IIT there will be an
407 altered state of consciousness, a weaker perception of blue. Thus IIT proposes that consciousness is
408 graded and that greater the information integration or Φ more conscious it is. We propose
409 consciousness to be a perception of self and the content of consciousness as a product of information
410 computation. If a system does not have the proposed computationally connected network, the
411 NCC, there will be no state of self existence, thus there will be no state of consciousness. IIT proposes
412 that any system, natural or artificial, with a high level of information integration can be conscious.
413 However, it does not specify a cut off value of Φ , the measure of information integration. We propose
414 that for a system to be conscious it should have access to its immediate past state, thus must have a
415 functional bi-directionally connected memory.

416 The Recurrent Processing Theory¹¹ proposes the presence of feed forward processing under attentional
417 influence, a localized recurrent processing unit and a widespread recurrent processing unit of
418 information. The localized recurrent processing of information is proposed to be the Neural Correlate
419 of Consciousness (NCC). However this theory fails to answer the questions of origin of the perception of
420 self existence and also the respective response generated to the incoming information from the external
421 modalities. There is no mention of any memory of NCC also. Our model holds that there will be
422 recurrent connections between the NCC and the auxiliary networks, as well as between the auxiliary
423 networks. However we also provide the existence of a memory of the NCC, which transiently stores the
424 content of a conscious perception, and is referenced and decoded by the NCC to generate the perception
425 of consciousness or self existence. Response is computed by the NCC to the respective information
426 received from the ANs and sent downstream to the other auxiliary networks for further processing.

427 Crick and Koch have given a neurobiological theory of consciousness⁴. They suggested that a
428 “working awareness” or conscious percept is formed by binding relevant neurons, selected by
429 attentional mechanism, together by synchronization of their activity in 40 Hz oscillations. They also
430 introduce a “binding problem” consisting of neurons that are computationally connected with an
431 unlimited, may be time limited, capacity to store information for a short period of time. The elements
432 required for binding are proposed to be stored into a short term working memory. In their paper “A
433 framework for consciousness”⁵, they mention the existence of “penumbra”, which they define as an
434 unconscious seat consisting of past states of NCC’s neurons, expected consequences and movements
435 computed by NCC. Also the penumbra neurons may project back to the NCC to support it. This short
436 term working memory and penumbra referenced directly correlates with our proposed model of the
437 working memory of the NCC. The working memory is bi-directionally connected to the NCC and
438 stores the information computed by the NCC in each cycle of its computation. The content of the
439 memory is also the content of the conscious perception. Even though the memory is unconscious in

440 nature,the decoding and referencing of the contents of memory by the NCC gives rise to the conscious
441 perception.

442 Finally we come to the discussion of the hard problem of consciousness¹.Have we solved it?Not
443 entirely. Do we think it is relevant?Not entirely. We provide a basic model of how consciousness can be
444 computed,how conscious perception is nothing but a simulation generated by the NCC and when we
445 can call a system conscious. We propose that information computed by the NCC is stored in the
446 memory in the format of “the organism is perceiving a particular cognitive domain”.Thus we do not
447 think that someone or something is experiencing any self existence,its just the way the memory stores
448 the information and the NCC decodes it to generate an illusion of self-existence or conscious
449 perception,giving the name of the proposed theory:The Self Simulation Theory.

450 There have been efforts in domain of neuro imaging and cognitive science to find out which
451 neuroanatomical regions or circuits are responsible for being the NCC. Studies have studied cortical
452 activation patterns under altered states of consciousness-anesthesia⁴⁷,sleep⁵⁰ and others. Network
453 analysis studies have suggested the existence of cortical hubs,which are areas of highest network
454 connectivity. These hubs have been reported to be interconnected and linked to a particular core
455 network,which when studied revealed to have similar components to that of the default mode network
456 of the brain⁴⁸⁻⁴⁹.Also the default mode network has been shown to have reduced connectivity under
457 anesthesia⁴⁷,supporting the claim of its plausible involvement in conscious perception. However in
458 order to understand the computational framework of NCC,the neural architecture of the brain needs to
459 be simulated. Brain neuronal simulations being carried out by École polytechnique fédérale de
460 Lausanne(EPFL),Switzerland under Blue Brain Project of the Swiss Brain Research Initiative⁶⁵,aim to
461 simulate the human brain neural architecture to understand neural network functions and explain
462 various neurobiological phenomenon. Perhaps after simulation of the entire neural architecture the
463 exact mechanism of computation of consciousness will be clear and our model can be validated.

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